

A benchmark and a multi-stage pipeline for classifying underwater videos at scale

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ARTICLE HISTORY

Compiled May 21, 2024

ABSTRACT

Standardised benchmarks have been crucial in driving the recent progress in computer vision. However, most benchmarks are designed for general-purpose tasks, covering multiple different topics and classes but are limited to the needs of specialised tasks. For example, when performing 3D reconstruction of corals, researchers need to record footage of coral with multiple camera angles. Due to the limited availability of such videos in standard datasets, the ability to reconstruct 3D coral models from public videos would alleviate this problem since it would allow researchers to tap into the vast scope of online content. Thus, one could use machine learning to sift through the immense amounts of content and automatically identify suitable videos for 3D reconstruction. In this work, we introduce a new benchmark that uses amateur footage queried from the YouTube-8M dataset where each video has been manually labelled for undersea, coral, and multiple camera angles. Furthermore, we construct a three-stage pipeline of machine learning models with the purpose of identifying suitable videos for 3D reconstruction of coral from the public domain. We instantiate the pipeline with state-of-the-art video classification methods and evaluate their performance on the benchmark, identifying their shortcomings and avenues for future research.

KEYWORDS

Benchmark; underwater; coral; computer vision; underwater video classification; underwater object detection; Deep learning; Transformers;

1. Introduction

The health of the world's oceans is under increasingly higher stress due to threats such as climate change, over-fishing, and pollution. Of the many unique ecosystems in the sea, coral reefs are among nature's most precious and most threatened treasures (Hoegh-Guldberg *et al.* 2007). Their vibrant colours and diverse life forms not only capture our imagination but also play a vital role in maintaining the overall balance of marine life. Marine conservation efforts are therefore at a critical juncture, and a deeper understanding of the current state of coral reefs is desperately needed (Hoegh-Guldberg *et al.* 2007). One method of expanding our knowledge comes in the form of creating three-dimensional graphical representations of coral structures (Rossi *et al.*

2021). These models can be used to determine how the structures of live coral provide habitats for marine life but also what happens to reef organisms when coral reefs are continuously impacted by outside disturbances (Gonzalez-Rivero *et al.* 2017).

These 3D models are usually constructed based on professionally obtained underwater footage, as several conditions must be fulfilled before a 3D model of sufficient quality can be produced. Some of the more important conditions are that the coral are viewed in two arcs of 180° perpendicular to one another (Ferrari *et al.* 2017). Furthermore, reference tools should be present in the footage for determining relative distances and true colours, such as colour code palettes and horizontal level indicators. Using such purposely acquired data allows for a 3D model that accurately simulates the sizes, colours, and angles of the ocean floor (Ferrari *et al.* 2017). However, the drawback is that these methods depend entirely on high-quality footage. This dependence is very limiting as vast amounts of amateur underwater videos are readily available on the internet. It is possible to construct 3D models from footage of an inferior quality. Still, at the very least, some of the conditions must be fulfilled, particularly the corals, which have to be viewed from multiple angles. This leaves the researchers with a time-consuming task, though, as it is likely only a few videos will contain the right conditions for coral reconstruction; therefore, sometimes, many will have to be watched and discounted before usable footage can be found.

Therefore, there is an unmet need for a method to bridge the gap between amateur footage and scientific research, allowing for the vast amounts of available amateur data to be utilised. One that might filter through large datasets of video data and isolate only the parts that might be of interest. One method of approaching this problem is to separate it into three tasks the tool would need to solve. The first is identifying which parts of the footage are underwater. The second task is to determine which part contains clear images of corals. Lastly, the tool would need to determine whether sufficient conditions are fulfilled, namely - viewing angles, for 3D reconstruction to realistically take place.

There is also the task of identifying whether or not the footage is actually undersea footage and there are multiple ways to determine whether footage or just an individual frame is underwater. A specialised method might not be required, and a general-purpose neural network might be all that is necessary as long as it is sufficiently trained on a diverse range of data (Wang *et al.* 2023).

One prominent method for identifying which segments of a video contain corals is object detection using machine learning models. There are a variety of these models, but one of the more common and effective methods they use is the two-stage framework. It works by combining object localisation to identify where the objects are in the frames and image classification to identify what the objects are. The model first generates a set of bounding boxes that may contain objects, then attempts to classify them, and finally, it might assign each object with a confidence rating (Moniruzzaman *et al.* 2017).

The last component is the camera motion detection model. Similar to underwater detection, a specialised method might not exist nor be necessary, and a general-purpose neural network is applied. However, in order to do this, sets of video data are needed both for training and testing purposes, particularly for the training of underwater detection and camera motion detection models. To the best of our knowledge, no currently existing data sets consisting of underwater videos of corals suits this particular task (Griffin and Corso 2021).

Therefore, in this paper, we propose a new benchmark dataset that has been created for these tasks. We further propose a pipeline using these three components for classifying videos that might be useful for coral 3D reconstruction. We employ state-

of-the-art machine learning models to instantiate these components and evaluate their performance over our new benchmark, discussing the results and possible avenues for improvement given these results.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 provides the background required for understanding the methods employed in this work, followed by a detailed view of related work (Section 3). Section 4 presents our underwater video benchmark and describes its construction. We then present the pipeline and its instantiation (Section 5), followed by an experimental evaluation of the proposed pipeline on our benchmark (Section 6). After discussing the results, we point out the limitations of this work and opportunities for future research (Section 6) and conclude in Section 7.

2. Background

Since the three main components of the pipeline are image classification, object classification and camera motion classification, this section presents some background on these three components.

2.1. Convolutional neural network

There are several valid approaches for the tasks of image classification and object detection. A Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) (Lecun *et al.* 1998) is a class of deep learning neural networks widely used in image analysis and classification. They have shown particular success in processing data with a grid-like topology, such as a 2D grid of pixel images. Therefore, they are used in many current state-of-the-art methods for image classification and object detection. One of the fundamental components of a CNN

Figure 1. The figure shows a convolutional neural network consisting of convolutional layers that put the input through convolutional filters, followed by a pooling layer, reducing the spatial dimensions of the input, and lastly, a fully-connected layer, which then, typically through a softmax activation function, maps to the output.

is the convolutional layers within its neural network structure. These layers perform operations called convolutions, which, in the field of classification, involve sliding one or multiple kernels over a square grid of pixels depending on the size of the kernels. The

dot product of the value of these pixels is calculated, and the kernel moves on, one pixel length at a time. After a convolutional layer, an activation layer immediately follows, which applies an activation function that allows for more non-linear relationships to be learned. ReLU (Rectified Linear Unit) is a commonly used activation function, which simply outputs all negative values as zero. This allows more complex features to be learned in the activation map (or feature map), which aids in identifying image features like edges, textures, and shapes.

In the shallow layers, the features are often simpler, but as the model moves further down the network, subsequent layers can learn to activate only on specific but more complex patterns consisting of these features. Depending on the model, numerous convolution and activation layers might be used to aid in identifying more complex patterns, but other layers are also essential. It is common practice for two convolution layers to be followed by a pooling layer which is interspersed between pairs of convolution layers to downsample the spatial dimensionality of the input for the following layers. In most CNN, this is done with a MAX function, which, through pooling layers, reduces the activation map to, e.g., 25% of its original size if using a 2X2 pooling layer. This is a destructive process as data is discarded but it is an essential step as it makes the network more robust to small variations in the input and greatly reduces the computational requirements of the model. It also allows the model to be resistant to over-fitting and to better capture variations in the positions of objects in an image (O’Shea and Nash 2015).

Another advantage to the CNN is that the spatial locations share the same kernels, meaning one pattern might be used for several locations in a single image, e.g., a pattern for the human silhouette might be used on multiple people anywhere in an image. Furthermore, the CNN model allows parameter sharing in the sense that it does not need to dedicate separate disjoint parameters for each pattern. This significantly reduces the required parameters compared to a fully connected network (O’Shea and Nash 2015).

2.2. *Transformer*

Another approach to solving image classification problems is a transformer model. Originally designed for natural language processing, transformer models have also been proven effective at image classification (Liu *et al.* 2021a) due to several key features of the Transformer architecture that align well with the requirements of image processing. The central innovation of the transformer model is the self-attention mechanism, which allows the model to weigh the significance of different parts of the input data.

The overall architecture of a transformer consists of an encoder and a decoder, two neural networks, each containing multiple layers (Vaswani *et al.* 2023). The encoder takes an input and converts it into a series of vectors, each representing different aspects of the input and capturing traits or regions of an image. An architectural diagram of a transformer can be seen in Figure 2.

The encoder consists of two types of sub-layers. The first is the self-attention mechanism, which is a central component of the model as it allows the encoder to focus disproportionately on selected parts of the input sequence. In the context of image classification, this would involve preprocessing the image such that it is separated into smaller, linearly embedded units called patches, which create a sequence of vector representations of different image regions. A vision transformer (ViT) (Dosovitskiy *et al.* 2021) might be used for this process, where images are treated similarly to text sequences. Then, positional encodings are added to the patches to retain information

Figure 2. Figure showing a transformer. Transformers consist of an encoder and a decoder. The encoder first performs positional encoding on the input. Then, a self-attention layer calculates the self-attention scores of the input. The self-attention scores are then put through a fully connected network. The decoder has a similar structure to the encoder, but the input consists of the sequence that the model is currently generating. It has two self-attention layers, where the second one also takes the encoder output as input (Vaswani *et al.* 2023).

about their original locations within the image. An attention function is then applied, which scores each patch based on three vectors, namely the query (Q), key (K), and value (V). The attention score for a pair of patches determines how much one patch should attend to another. It's computed as the dot product of the query vector of one patch and the key vector of another. The output is a weighted sum of the value vectors of all patches, where the weights are the attention scores. This process can be repeated iteratively in multi-layered transformers to allow for increasingly powerful representations. The attention layers follow a fully connected Feed-Forward network, which transforms the output of the attention layer through two linear transformations and an activation function, typically ReLU. It is also worth noting that each layer has a normalisation step, and its output is added to the layer's input before being passed on.

The decoder is structured similarly to the encoder, though the input consists of the sequence that the model is currently generating. Furthermore, the self-attention layer is masked, as it contains a masking mechanism to ensure that the prediction for a certain position only depends on the known outputs of positions before it (Vaswani *et al.* 2023). In language generation models, the masking step is crucial, as the words must be generated based on preceding words and not future ones. This step, however, is not always required in pure classification tasks, as the positional order of the input is not relevant. Following the masking layer, another attention layer receives the encoder output as input. By receiving the queries from the masked attention layer and the keys and values from the encoder, the decoder determines which parts of the input sequence hold the greater relevance (Vaswani *et al.* 2023). Given the purpose of the decoder,

transformer models applied to image classification tasks do not need it. Instead, they rely entirely on the encoder, where the model is also adapted to handle two-dimensional image data (Liu *et al.* 2021a).

3. Related work

This section reviews related work with regard to methods for video classification, underwater object detection, camera motion classification, and other benchmark datasets.

3.1. Video classification methods

In CNN approaches, the small windows of kernels limit the potential for modelling long-range interactions which is important in the context of our task. For instance, classifying whether a video contains real underwater footage requires the ability to model long-range interactions, as small distant parts of the video may contain clues needed for the classification. Therefore we focus on approaches that use self-attention. VTN (Neimark *et al.* 2021) uses a pre-trained Vision Transformer (ViT) (Dosovitskiy *et al.* 2021) model with the addition of a temporal attention encoder and achieves competitive results in various video classification benchmarks. TubeViT (Piergiovanni *et al.* 2022) adapts the ViT model for both image and video classification by introducing the notion of sparse video tubes, which allow the model to sample and classify based on small patches of the input data, and it also supports the usage of a pre-trained ViT model. Video Swin Transformer (Liu *et al.* 2021b) introduces the concept of inductive bias of locality from Swin Transformer (Liu *et al.* 2021a) for video classification, and it does so by making the patches and window partitioning three-dimensional. Being derived from the Swin Transformer, it supports using a pre-trained Swin Transformer as a base and training the new model from adapted parameters. Both TubeViT and Video Swin Transformer achieve state-of-the-art performance on various video classification benchmarks, including Kinetics-400. Some approaches for video classification consider multiple modalities, such as audio and text. Generally, multi-modal approaches have a dedicated fusion layer where the encoded modalities are fused (Jiang *et al.* 2021). MAF (Zheng *et al.* 2023) implements neural architecture search to get the best self-attention representation and fusion for audio and video inputs using a long-short-term memory (LSTM) model as the underlying classification model. OmniVec (Srivastava and Sharma 2023) proposes a network architecture that separately encodes each modality, has a shared backbone network based on ViT, and includes task-specific heads. OmniVec is therefore able to train and adapt the model for different tasks sequentially.

3.2. Object detection models

For underwater object detection which may be used to detect individual corals, models based on YOLO (Redmon *et al.* 2016), R-CNN (Girshick *et al.* 2014), AlexNet (Krizhevsky *et al.* 2017) are the most prevalent (Zaidi *et al.* 2022). Notably, YOLO-based models have had multiple iterations with improvements in each of them. For the task at hand, YOLO-based models are the most relevant, as they are made for object detection and classification in real-time. The ability to classify videos in real-time implies low inference time. Low inference time is useful in tasks where a large amount of videos needs to be considered. The newest iteration YOLOv8 (Jocher *et al.* 2023) achieves

close to state-of-the-art performance in the COCO object classification dataset while retaining real-time classification speeds. There are variants of YOLO specifically for underwater object detection. YOLOv7-AC (Liu *et al.* 2023) and U-YOLOv7 (Yu *et al.* 2023) modify the original YOLOv7 (Wang *et al.* 2022) model. YOLOv7-AC utilises a ACmixBlock module to replace the 3×3 convolution block in the E-ELAN structure. Furthermore, YOLOv7-AC utilises a global attention mechanism in the backbone and head parts of the architecture. YOLOv7-AC uses the K-means++ algorithm instead of K-means to obtain anchor boxes. U-YOLOv7 approach this differently by first instantiating a network that combines CrossConv and an efficient squeeze-excitation module to reduce the amount of parameters, and improve feature fusion. Then, U-YOLOv7 utilises the Content-Aware ReAssembly of FEatures (CARAFE) operator to extract more semantic information about underwater images before feature fusion. A 3D attention mechanism is applied to improve U-YOLOv7’s resilience to noise in underwater detection. YOLOv7-AC and U-YOLOv7 achieve marginally better performance than the original YOLOv7 in different datasets, respectively.

3.3. *Camera motion models*

The task of classifying videos based on their camera movement using deep learning is a relatively new one. We attempt to classify the camera motion in order to determine if a coral is viewed from multiple angles. The more traditional approaches are based on the calculation of motion vectors between subsequent frames. These motion vectors can then be analysed to estimate the type of camera motion. This approach is used for higher-level parametric models that globally describe the camera motion. However, the heuristics these models utilise are too straightforward for a more general and reliable camera motion classification method (Ouenniche *et al.* 2021). Some newer approaches have taken a different route and have made use of deep neural networks for camera motion classification. More specifically, CNNs, both 2D and 3D, have seen success with this task. Pavan *et al.* (2022) achieve an accuracy of 98% on H.264/AVC encoded video sequences using a 2D CNN structure. Their method consists of extracting block motion vectors from compressed videos, modelling these vectors using the HSI colour model. The HSI colour model is colour model where HSI stands for hue, saturation, and intensity. The HSI assignment is then converted to an RGB image, and lastly, that image is fed to their network. An example of a method using a 3D CNN can be seen in (Ouenniche *et al.* 2021). The method presented in this paper achieves an average accuracy of 94% on their own dataset made up of videos collected from different movies and YouTube. It should be noted that the validation set used in this paper is rather large, with hundreds of video segments in each class of camera movement, as well as containing a large variety of videos taken under differing conditions. This points to the amount of generalisation of this particular 3D CNN method.

3.4. *Other benchmarks*

The field of coral 3D reconstruction is not a new one (Beall *et al.* 2010, Nurtantio Andono *et al.* 2012); however, typically, these projects rely on data collection done with specialised equipment, such as ROVs and multiple-camera systems (De Oliveira *et al.* 2021). This data often consists of still images (Nurtantio Andono *et al.* 2012, Lin *et al.* 2014), but with additional data types such as coordinates, depth and temperatures (Bewley *et al.* 2015). The vast majority of raw undersea footage available online do not

consist of such high quality images nor is it attached with the other relevant data one might use in 3D reconstruction. Therefore, it would not make sense to train detection and classification models, with the goal of identifying suitable online videos for 3D coral reconstruction, on existing, traditional data for 3D coral reconstruction. To the best of our knowledge, there is no publicly available dataset containing video footage of coral structures from multiple angles, particularly not any consisting of amateur footage. Therefore, as a part of this work, we created a new dataset of underwater coral videos. There are a number of places from which to source the raw videos for such a dataset. Kinetics (Kay *et al.* 2017a) and UFC101 (Soomro *et al.* 2012) are large and recognised video datasets, but they focus on human actions in particular. In this work, we choose YouTube-8M (Abu-El-Haija *et al.* 2016) as a basis for our benchmark, as it contains a large number of videos (approximately 8 million), including a substantial amount of underwater videos. Furthermore, the availability of a keyword query mechanism allows one to better identify potential videos, as was done for this benchmark.

4. An underwater, coral, and camera motion detection benchmark

One of the challenges with building a model for identifying videos that can be used for 3D reconstruction was the lack of data. Therefore, we manually created our own dataset of videos. This benchmark consists of amateur videos, where we manually identified the segments of these videos containing underwater footage and coral. Furthermore, we identified the segments where the footage seemed to focus on a particular coral object and viewed it from more than one angle. Therefore, each video in the dataset contains a description identifying if and which segments of a video are taken undersea, whether it contains corals, and whether it has a multiple-angle view of any corals.

To the best of our knowledge, the proposed benchmark represents the first attempt to utilise publicly-available user-generated videos for coral 3D reconstruction. This data is used both for training and validation and as a benchmark for the models of the pipeline. The videos were retrieved from the YouTube-8M (Abu-El-Haija *et al.* 2016) dataset by filtering the dataset on specific labels. For undersea coral videos the dataset was queried for videos containing the labels “coral”, “underwater”, and not “aquarium”. This yielded 287 videos that contain coral and undersea footage. The videos from YouTube-8M are typically 2 to 8 minutes long. To approximate the class distribution of videos when directly importing from YouTube, YouTube was queried three times with the following phrases “Coral reef”, “Underwater Diving” and “Underwater”. 100 videos from every query were then manually checked to see which classes the video belonged to. The class density of the videos was averaged from the three queries and simulated in the dataset. The averages came up to 40% of the benchmark videos containing neither corals nor undersea footage and where 60% contains both, but from which 13% are footage from aquariums and not natural coral reefs. The importance of including videos from aquariums in the dataset is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 compares coral from an aquarium and coral from undersea videos, showcasing how distinguishing between the sea and an aquarium can sometimes be challenging. In this particular example, the aquarium picture is significantly darker. Furthermore, often footage from aquariums will show support structures (e.g., beams, walls, glass, etc.). However, that is not always the case.

A subset of the videos that are both undersea and contain coral have also been classified according to the camera movement in the video. For a video to be a good candidate for 3D reconstruction, there must be frames of the same coral from multiple angles.

Figure 3. A comparison between frames showing coral filmed in an aquarium and coral filmed undersea. While often videos from aquariums are easily distinguished from videos filmed undersea, this is not always the case as shown above.

Figure 4. Pictures showing ideal camera motion around a coral. Ideally, the camera motion consists of a pivot around the coral structure, showing as much of the structure as possible.

Ideally, the shot would be an 360-degree pivot around the coral, showing the full coral structure. However, in our experience a shot like this rarely occurs in YouTube videos of corals. In about 220 videos from the dataset containing undersea corals, we found no video segments containing this exact type of footage. For this reason, we had to soften the requirements for what we consider as acceptable camera motion to collect any meaningful amount of data. The softened requirement is simply whether multiple angles of the same coral are shown. Figure 4 shows an example of one of the higher quality shots we found. In the 220 videos, we found 53 videos, with 112 segments, showing a coral/coral structure from multiple angles.

Figure 5 shows a flowchart of the creation of the dataset. The number of videos containing undersea and coral footage is the same, since every video that contained undersea footage also contained footage of coral. The average lengths of the underwater, coral, and camera motion segments are about 127, 39, and 13 seconds respectively.

Figure 5. Figure showing a flowchart for the creation of the dataset. Firstly we filtered the YouTube 8M dataset to find underwater videos. These videos were then manually classified into segments containing undersea footage. Then segments containing coral was classified, and finally coral segments showing multiple angles of a coral were classified.

Figure 6. Pipeline structure for classifying videos that can be used for 3D reconstruction of coral. The pipeline uses videos found in online sources, e.g., YouTube, as input and then detects which parts are filmed undersea. Then the undersea video parts detected in the first step are put through a coral classifier to determine whether they contain coral. The parts containing coral then go through a camera motion classifier to detect whether they contain the correct camera motion.

5. A Multi-angle Coral Video Detection Pipeline

This section describes the structure of our proposed public video classification pipeline and the underlying methods used in the pipeline. The pipeline consists of three machine learning models in sequence: a model that detects whether a video contains actual undersea footage, a stage that detects whether a video contains coral, and finally, a stage that detects whether the camera motion in a video is sufficient for 3D reconstruction. This is shown in Figure 6, where YouTube videos are put through a set of classifiers to obtain a set of videos and frames that are relevant for 3D coral model reconstruction.

5.1. Undersea classifier

The task of classifying whether a video contains undersea footage is a video classification task. We chose the Video Swin Transformer (Liu *et al.* 2021b) as it is suited for the task while also being a state-of-the-art model for video classification. Furthermore, we find that a multi-modal approach is unnecessary, as most videos do not have any relevant text, and the audio is mostly music and generally irrelevant to classifying whether a video is underwater or not. Video Swin Transformer is primarily based on the original Swin Transformer (Liu *et al.* 2021a), so it follows similar building blocks: 3D patch partitioning, 3D shifted windows, multi-head self-attention, and 3D relative position bias. Video Swin Transformer’s architecture consists of first 3D patch partitioning across video frames and then four stages of $2\times$ spatial downsampling in a patch merging layer of each stage. This is shown in Figure 7 with the dimensions of the inputs/outputs for each layer.

We use the tiny architecture of Video Swin Transformer (Swin-T) as presented by (Liu *et al.* 2021b), as the classification task is binary, and it is therefore not necessary to use the larger variants. In Swin-T; C is 96, and the stage 3 layer size is 6. The larger Video Swin architectures vary the 3rd stage size and C . The Video Swin Transformer

Figure 7. Video Swin Tiny architecture overview (Liu *et al.* 2021b). Video Swin Tiny consists of a 3D patch partitioning layer, that splits a video into 3D patches, which are then linearly embedded, and then put through several transformer blocks that perform multi-head self-attention in 3D shifted windows.

block consists of 3D shifted windows based multi-head self-attention, and is the major change made to adapt regular Swin Transformer for video classification. We use a model that is pre-trained on the Kinetics400 dataset (Kay *et al.* 2017a), and adapt the last feature to class mapping layer to map to a single class {not undersea, undersea} by replacing the last linear layer that maps from 768 features to 400 classes with a linear layer that maps from 768 features to 1 class. The result of the linear layer is run through a sigmoid activation function to guarantee that the model’s output is between 0 and 1 and to allow for non-linear and more complex relationships to be captured. We describe and evaluate this process in more detail in Section 6.

5.2. Coral classifier

For detecting corals in videos, we use YOLOv8 (Jocher *et al.* 2023). This model is primarily intended to be used for object detection in videos, but the authors adapted it for various other tasks, such as image classification in videos (Jocher *et al.* 2023). YOLOv8 is based on YOLOv5’s (Jocher 2020) architecture, which possesses the ability to automatically learn anchor boxes for any given dataset (Zaidi *et al.* 2022). As we do not need to know where the coral is in a given frame, using YOLOv8 for classification is sufficient. Furthermore, the YOLOv8 model we use is pre-trained on the ImageNet dataset (Ultralytics 2023), which contains a *coral* label. We chose this model for the coral classification task because of the availability of a pre-trained model, and the inference speed (Ultralytics 2023). In our implementation, we check whether the top 5 predictions contain the *coral* label. Additionally, YOLO-based models have been shown to have competitive results in adaptations for undersea object detection (Sung *et al.* 2017, Xu *et al.* 2023). We use the smallest version of YOLOv8 classifier (YOLOv8n-cls) for this component.

5.3. Camera motion classifier

For the camera motion classifier, we again use the Video Swin Transformer (Liu *et al.* 2021b) that is pre-trained on Kinetics400 (Kay *et al.* 2017a). Just as with the undersea classifier, the last layer of the camera motion classifier was replaced so that the last layer only maps to one class, with that class being whether the camera motion showed multiple angles of a coral.

6. Experimental evaluation

In this section, we present the performance of the proposed pipeline and its components, described in Section 5, on our proposed benchmark, which is described in Section 4. Additionally, we describe the methodology we used to test the models on the benchmark and our method for hyperparameter search. Lastly, the results are discussed.

Each model is trained and tested on its respective part of the benchmark. This means that all of the classifiers are trained and run in isolation and not on the identified videos from previous parts of the pipeline. For example, the coral classifier is run on the part of the benchmark containing undersea footage and not only on the videos that were identified by the undersea classifier. This ensures that the pipeline structure does not introduce bias from video classification in the previous steps.

Dataset splits and setting

For the undersea video classifier, we use roughly 10% of the whole benchmark for training and roughly 5% for validation. The remaining 85% is used for testing. This split is not usual, but we chose this due to memory constraints and to avoid over-fitting. Although the videos are chosen randomly, we still make sure to include the same video distribution that was described in Section 4 in both the training and validation sets. Each video is split into at most 10-second long segments, and each segment has a label assigned to it (0 or 1), depending on whether that segment contains undersea footage in the benchmark set. Furthermore, each segment is reduced to exactly 80 frames by skipping some frames, a number which we found by checking the lowest possible frame rate of a video and lowest possible segment length. This is done due to GPU memory constraints to lower the computation time and account for the fact that the dataset the model is pre-trained on (Kinetics400) consists of mostly ten-second videos (Kay *et al.* 2017b). Our labelling process was based on the timeline (in minutes and seconds), and not the frame at which undersea footage starts. Therefore, we ignore the segments that start or end within that one-second margin. Finally, the training set consists of 766 video segments, which are a varying mix of undersea and not undersea footage. Please note that due to the pre-processing of the videos, i.e the splitting of the videos into 10-second segments, the segment amounts in this section no longer correspond to Figure 5. During training, it was found to be detrimental to the performance of the model if the training set was larger. Although we have not tested this due to memory constraints, this could potentially be fixed by adjusting the hyperparameters, such as batch size and learning rate, so the model’s parameter updates during the training phase were less volatile. Pre-processing (frame rescaling and normalisation) is done before training and testing. Each frame is resized to a 224×224 matrix and normalised using the mean and standard deviation of the RGB values of the frames. As required by the classifier, the tensors are arranged as $B \times C \times T \times W \times H$ where B is the mini-batch size, C is the colour dimension (3), T is the temporal dimension (80), W is the width of the frame (224), and H is the height of the frame (224). We use sharpness-aware minimisation (Foret *et al.* 2021) with stochastic-gradient-descent as the optimiser, and binary cross-entropy loss as the loss function.

The undersea classifier is run on test set. The test set retains the video distribution as described in Section 4. As with training, each video is split into at most 10 second segments. This results in 4858 segments which contain undersea footage, and 4823 which do not. Naturally, despite the amount of videos containing undersea footage

being larger on video level, video segments which do not contain any undersea footage are plentiful in numbers, as videos containing undersea footage also contain the other. As for the camera motion data, the pre-processed training set consists of 476 video segments, of which 101 segments are positive. The validation set consists of 73 segments, of which 13 are positive. The test set consists of 230 segments, of which 39 are positive. This comes out to a split consisting of 61% of the data being used for training, 9% for validation, and 30% for testing. In order to overcome the class imbalance in the camera motion data, we used random undersampling for the negative class.

The pre-processing steps and the optimiser for the camera motion model are the same as for the underwater model. The camera motion model is also pre-trained on the Kinetics400 dataset.

Hyperparameter search

There are a few hyperparameters we can change for the training. For the undersea classifier, these hyperparameters are batch size, learning rate, momentum, weight decay, epochs, and whether we fine-tune the original pre-trained model or only train the linear layer we add. We use the Weights & Biases (W&B) technique (Biewald 2020) for hyperparameter search by setting up a possible value range for each hyperparameter and letting W&B try different combinations with the goal of trying to get the F1 score on the validation set to be as high as possible. W&B is set up to do this using Bayesian optimisation with 30 attempts. For the undersea video classifier, the best hyperparameters within our defined ranges are found to be the ones in Table 1. Furthermore, we also try to fine-tune the pre-trained part of the network after training the linear layer we add. We find that in the case of an undersea classifier, doing so generally hurts the performance of the model. However, this could be attributed to the fact that we do not use a lot of the benchmark as training data, and we have memory constraints with respect to how much we can batch simultaneously, so this could be examined further. After the training, the hyperparameter configuration is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Hyperparameters for undersea and camera motion classifiers, found through hyperparameter search. The search used Bayesian optimisation, and was given 30 attempts to find the best hyperparameters.

	Undersea	Camera motion
Batch size	3	4
Learning rate	0.00088	0.0091
Momentum	0.98	0.93
Weight decay	0.002	0.0017
Epochs	4	12

For the camera motion classifier, we train the model’s last linear layer, like the undersea classifier. As with the undersea model, we use W&B to search for hyperparameters, with the same possible hyperparameters and the same 30 attempts to find the best ones. Hyperparameters for training the linear layer are the ones presented in Table 1.

Results

The performance of the undersea model is shown in Figure 8(b). We observe that more video segments were falsely classified as not undersea (false negatives), relative to videos being falsely classified as undersea (false positives). This potentially indicates that the model is proficient at classifying real undersea footage, and has decent proficiency in deciding that aquarium footage is not undersea. To investigate this, we run the model only on the video segments that come from aquarium videos. There is a total of 1257 video segments from the videos that contain aquarium footage. We observe that a relatively small number of video segments are falsely classified as undersea: 126 out of 1257 video segments.

The camera motion model was run on the test set, consisting of 30% of the total camera motion data. The performance is shown in Figure 8(b). The model achieved an F1 score of 0.41. This shows that the model had difficulties capturing the pattern we wanted it to capture. These results were achieved without fine-tuning the model. We found that with fine-tuning, the model could not classify any of the positive video segments and achieved an F1 score of 0.

Hits	Count	Undersea	Coral	Camera motion
False positives	126	F1 Score 0.93	0.84	0.41
True negatives	1131	Precision 0.96	0.79	0.44
		Recall 0.90	0.89	0.38

(a) Analysis of undersea classifier on only aquarium videos. (b) Performance of undersea, coral, and camera motion classifiers.

Figure 8. Results of running the three models on their respective parts of the benchmark. 8(a) shows an analysis of running the undersea classifier on aquarium videos. 8(b) shows the performance of undersea, coral, and camera motion classifiers.

Discussion and limitations

For the undersea classifier, the class balance is balanced, with roughly 50% of the video segments being undersea, and not undersea. This falls in line with the expectation that a binary classifier works best when the class balance is 50% of one class, and 50% of the other. As described earlier, we built the model with hardware limitations. For instance, there are bigger variants of the Video Swin Transformer model, but their size would limit us to only being able to process one or two video segments at a time. We expect that the model would also be able to perform better if it was trained with a larger batch size, as we limited the batch size parameter to a maximum of 8. Additionally, more data from the benchmark, being able to consider more than 10 seconds per video segment, and possibly more epochs would have helped fine-tune the pre-trained part of the model and could possibly achieve better performance than what we got from just training the last linear layer. The undersea classifier performs well in classifying the undersea part of the benchmark and performs better than what we expected in classifying aquarium videos as not undersea. The low amount of false positives is promising, the much higher amount of false negatives could potentially be solved by scaling up the model, or being able to properly fine-tune the pre-trained part of it.

For the coral classifier, the performance is as expected from the smallest YOLOv8 classification model (Ultralytics 2023). It is important to note that if a video was filmed in an aquarium, we did not label the videos as containing coral. This introduces some

amount of noise in the benchmark data. Additionally, due to the fact that the benchmark generally consists of low-quality underwater videos, it is sometimes impossible to tell whether some frames contain coral or not, which might be reflected in our labelling process and the classifier results. However, the performance of coral classification is satisfactory, and it could be improved by either choosing another model or cleaning up the input data.

The camera motion classifier performed rather poorly. We believe this can be attributed to the size of the benchmark for the camera motion data, and the chosen model not being able to handle this task well. The data amount remains challenging, and techniques that are able to learn from few samples may perform better. The data representing the positive class was very sparse in our dataset, making the negative class extremely over-represented. Because of this class imbalance, we could not be as strict as we would have liked when classifying camera motion in our dataset, because we would have too few true positives. This probably blurred the line between what data should belong to the positive class and what should belong to the negative. In trying to alleviate the class balance problem, we chose to do an undersampling of the negative data points. However, as the overall amount of data is quite small, and some video segments much better represented the kind of camera motion we were looking for, it might have been more appropriate to oversample positive segments, specifically of the ones of very high quality. Furthermore, it is important to note that given the nature of the benchmark data, there is a limit to how high the models can score in tests measuring accuracy of any kind. Considering the sparsity of the data, one avenue worth exploring could be the utilisation of techniques such as few-shot learning. (Deng *et al.* 2023) utilise few-shot learning for video classification by introducing Dual-Hierarchy Graph Neural Network to model cross-video matching and video relations. Additionally, when identifying which footage contained coral and which footage contained the desired camera motion, there is a high level of inherent ambiguity. For example, when identifying coral in low-quality footage, it is difficult to determine when exactly a coral goes from being a blurred smudge in the distance to becoming an identifiable object, likewise with camera motion detection. Since nearly all footage is filmed freehand, technically, every coral is filmed from multiple angles, as the camera is in constant motion. When exactly a coral is viewed from angles, that are sufficiently different, can be difficult to determine; therefore, this data also suffers from a degree of uncertainty. Taken together, it seems that all the models will be limited in the scores they can achieve in any accuracy testing. Lastly, the 10-second limit of the segments probably also played a role in the performance, as 10 seconds would not always be enough to capture all the information from a single camera motion instance.

There are a few interesting problems raised by the challenge of 3D coral reconstruction that are beyond the scope of this work. As mentioned above, 3D reconstruction includes using tools to get various reference metrics, such as the scale, the colour coding, and the horizontal level (Ferrari *et al.* 2017). Including data with images that include such measurement tools in the benchmark would be beneficial.

7. Conclusion

In this paper, our goal was to create a benchmark for classifying videos that can be used for coral 3D model reconstruction. We manually labelled publicly available amateur footage from the YouTube-8M dataset, to find the segments of the videos containing undersea, coral, and multi-angle coral footage. We found 287 videos (589 and 1155

segments respectively), containing undersea and coral footage. Of these 287 videos, 53 videos (112 segments), contained examples of multi-angle coral footage. We tested classification models for the different aspects of the dataset and found that existing methods cover some parts of the task well, while some parts are not well addressed. Notably, coral classification is well covered by both existing datasets and the available models, achieving an F1 score of 0.84. Undersea classification is an unusual task that can be solved with an F1 score of 0.93 by adapting existing methods such as Video Swin Transformer. State-of-the-art video classification models used in underwater camera motion classification seem to be unable to capture the movement patterns in our benchmark entirely, achieving an F1 score of 0.41. Therefore, the benchmark is challenging and representative of the task.

Acknowledgements

This work was partially supported by the Data Science Research Center at the University of Haifa through the Israel PBC grant *Advancing Data Science to Serve Humanity and Protect the Global Environment* (grant no. 100009443)

Disclosure statement

The authors declare that they have no relevant or material financial interests that relate to the research described in this paper.

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